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D5.3 Policy Extraction and Recommendations Toolkit V1

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
CRISP-DM	Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
UI	User Interface

Executive summary

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project delivers, validates, demonstrates and promotes a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. It supports the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies.

WP3, WP4, WP5 are the core technical work-packages of the project, which focus on three independent and complementary streams of technological work driven by the technical specifications and the AI4PublicPolicy platform architecture provided by WP2. WP5 will deliver a set of AI solutions and the core outcome of the project, the Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will integrate an open environment for analytics and will provide the unique point for policymakers to access resources.

This deliverable describes the first version of the Policy Extraction Toolkit component, developed in the context of task T5.3 "AI Policy Extraction and Recommendations". This component is in charge of providing a toolkit for extracting data-driven policies based on selected AI algorithms (including Machine Learning, Deep Learning and Reinforcement learning) to estimate and recommend the parameters of the policy models, based on the policy datasets.

The Policy extraction and recommendation toolkit is implemented on top of an Open Analytical Environment and based on an industry-driven methodology called Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM). In the AI-based Policy making process proposed by the AI4PublicPolicy project the Policy Extraction toolkit addresses the steps from 3 to 5 (Policy Extraction phase) of the CRISP-DM methodology.

The Policy Extraction phase starts from the policy and the datasets retrieved through the "Policy and Data Management" component and provides AI Models and dashboards as an outcome. This process involves two actors: the Policy Maker and the AI Expert and all of the steps that need to be performed by them to achieve the goal of creating the policy's AI models.

The Open Analytical Environment it's the core of the toolkit which all the functionalities are built on. It allows a data scientist to work on the data preparation, run experiments, build AI pipelines to train models which later are used by a policy maker to design a policy.

Two categories of state-of-the-art solutions were analyzed: codeless platforms (such as KNIME, Node-RED and Streampipes) and code-centric solutions (JupyterHub, AirFlow, MLFlow). After performing the analysis of the state of the art solutions, we found none of them fully met our requirements and therefore we decided to design our system around several independent sub-components, each one implementing some specific requirements: User interface, Code Repository, Open Analytical Environment, Pipeline Manager, Model Manager.

After comparing the available options we have chosen the following software tools for our first implementation: JupyterHub (as an open analytical environment), MLFlow (for model and pipeline management), GitLab (as a code repository).

A future roadmap is to improve current features and add new features based on the feedback from the users (AI experts and policy makers) after the initial technical validation.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens' participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project's AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project's developments. AI4PublicPolicy's business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project's platform.

1.2 Description of Work Package 5, "Cloud-based AI Tools for Citizen Centric & Autonomous Policy Making"

WP5 will deliver a set of AI solutions and the core outcome of the project, the Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will integrate an open environment for analytics and will provide the unique point for policymakers to access resources. Thus, the main objectives of this WP are to:

1. Analyse various datasets to obtain actionable insights through AI tools that range from sentiment analysis and text analytics to opinion mining and policy recommendations.
2. Include citizens in the loop of policies implementation through a citizen-centric approach to obtain feedback and continuously evaluate and optimize the policies.
3. Deliver the policy management environment (VPME) for creating, customizing, linking / comparing, simulating, evaluating and optimizing policies.
4. Provide the required computing and data resources for performing the aforementioned AI analytics by dynamically allocating the required cloud resources.

1.3 Relation to other WPs and tasks

WP3, WP4, WP5 are the core technical work-packages of the project, which focus on three independent and complementary streams of technological work driven by the technical specifications and the AI4PublicPolicy platform architecture provided by WP2.

WP5 integrates the results from WP3 and WP4 with the AI tools, the Open Analytical environment and the citizens-centric optimization and provides to the Pilot tasks of WP6 the interfaces to access resources and interact with the Platform.

Finally WP5 feeds WP7 with the AI tools and the AI-based policy making artifacts (e.g. AI pipelines and AI models) for the Market Platform and WP8 with useful content to disseminate the AI-based policy making approach.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.1 Purpose and scope of this deliverable

This deliverable describes the first version of the Policy Extraction Toolkit component developed in the context of task T5.3 “AI Policy Extraction and Recommendations”.

This component is in charge of providing a toolkit for extracting data-driven policies based on selected AI algorithms (including Machine Learning, Deep Learning and Reinforcement learning) to estimate and recommend the parameters of the policy models, based on the policy datasets.

It provides information about the requirements, the design and finally the implementation based on the state-of-the-art tools analyzed and draws the roadmap for future developments.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

- The **first chapter** of the document is an introduction to the project and the document.
- The **second chapter** of the document is the background and state-of-the-art
- The **third chapter** of the document reports the functional requirements
- The **fourth chapter** of the document presents the solution design
- The **fifth chapter** presents the implementation of the demonstrator
- Finally, the document includes a fifth chapter with the conclusions

2 Background and State of the Art

The Policy extraction and recommendation toolkit is implemented on top of an Open Analytical Environment and based on the CRISP-DM methodology.

1.3 CRISP-DM methodology

In 2000, as response to common issues and needs, an industry-driven methodology called Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) was introduced as an alternative to Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD), a previous data mining methodology [CRISP-DM]. It also consolidated the original KDD model and its various extensions. The iterative executions of CRISP-DM stand as the most distinguishing feature compared to initial KDD that assumes a sequential execution of its steps. CRISP-DM, much like KDD, aims at providing practitioners with guidelines to perform data mining on large datasets.

The main steps of CRISP-DM, as depicted in Figure 3 below are as follows:

Figure 2. CRISP-DM Methodology

- **Step 1:** Business understanding: The focus of the first step is to gain an understanding of the project objectives and requirements from a business perspective followed by converting these into data mining problem definitions. Presentation of a preliminary plan to achieve the objectives are also included in this first step.
- **Step 2:** Data understanding: This step begins with an initial data collection and proceeds with activities in order to get familiar with the data, identify data quality issues, discover first insights into the data, and potentially detect and form hypotheses.

- **Step 3:** Data preparation: The third step covers activities required to construct the final dataset from the initial raw data. Data preparation tasks are performed repeatedly.
- **Step 4:** Modeling phase: In this step, various modeling techniques are selected and applied followed by calibrating their parameters. Typically, several techniques are used for the same data mining problem.
- **Step 5:** Evaluation of the model(s): The fifth step begins with the quality perspective and then, before proceeding to final model deployment, ascertains that the model(s) achieves the business objectives. At the end of this phase, a decision should be reached on how to use data mining results.
- **Step 6:** Deployment phase: In the final step, the models are deployed to enable end-customers to use the data as basis for decisions, or support in the business process. Even if the purpose of the model is to increase knowledge of the data, the knowledge gained will need to be organized, presented, and distributed in a way that the end-user can use it. Depending on the requirements, the deployment phase can be as simple as generating a report or as complex as implementing a repeatable data mining process.

In the AI-based Policy making process proposed by the AI4PublicPolicy project the Policy Extraction toolkit addresses the steps from 3 to 5 (Policy Extraction phase).

Figure 3. AI4PublicPolicy Policy making Process

1.4 Open Analytical Environment

It's the core of the toolkit which all the functionalities are built on. It allows a data scientist to work on the data preparation, run experiments, build AI pipelines to train models which later are used by a policy maker to design a policy.

This section provides an overview of the state-of-the-art platforms and tools that facilitate a data scientist and a policy maker in the process of designing a policy based on the available datasets and a selected AI model.

There are two main groups of available solutions to achieve this goal. First one is low-code solutions (analytical environments) where the main tool for building AI pipelines is a visual designer with an integrated library of AI models, execution environment, pipelines manager and visualization functionality.

There are several analytical environments available on the market. Some of them provide a full spectrum of AI tools (e.g. KNIME, Orange): visual AI pipeline designer, catalog of common AI models, pipeline management features. Some other tools are more generic: they could be used in a wider context (not just AI-related workflow, e.g. Apache Streampipes). Those tools usually provide less AI-specific features, but they could have other benefits such as more flexibility, better licensing schemes (could be free or open source).

Table 1 shows the summary of the low-code tools that we have analyzed.

Table 1. Open Analytical low-code tools

Platform	Language	License	Price	Owner	Cloud
KNIME	Codeless	Open Source/ Commercial	25K - 45K EUR (yearly)	KNIME	AWS, Azure, on-premise
Streampipes	JVM	Open Source	Free	Apache	on-premise
Orange	Python	Open Source	Free	University of Ljubljana	no
Node-RED	Codeless, JavaScript	Open Source	Free	OpenJS Foundation	All major cloud providers + on premise

KNIME is free and open-source data analytics, reporting and integration platform. KNIME integrates various components for machine learning and data mining through its modular data pipelining "Building Blocks of Analytics" concept. A graphical user interface and use of JDBC allows assembly of nodes blending different data sources, including preprocessing (ETL: Extraction, Transformation, Loading), for modeling, data analysis and visualization without, or with only minimal, programming.

Apache StreamPipes is a self-service (Industrial) IoT toolbox to enable non-technical users to connect, analyze and explore IoT data streams.

Orange is an open-source data visualization, machine learning and data mining toolkit. It features a visual programming front-end for explorative rapid qualitative data analysis and interactive data visualization.

Node-RED is a flow-based development tool for visual programming developed originally by IBM for wiring together hardware devices, APIs and online services as part of the Internet of Things. Node-RED provides a web browser-based flow editor, which can be used to create JavaScript functions. Elements of applications can be saved or shared for re-use. The runtime is built on Node.js.

Second group of available solutions are more code-intensive (mainly Python-centric). Those tools don't provide an out-of-the-box analytical environment with all features integrated. So the features such as the execution environment, AI models library or visualization are not integrated in one software product. To achieve that a manual integration of several tools is required. Example of such

a solution is a Jupyter Notebook which could be integrated with MLFlow (tracking models and experiments) and AirFlow (creating and scheduling executions of pipelines).

Table 2 shows the comparison of the code-centric tools that we have analyzed. They are not mutually exclusive: it's possible to integrate and to use them together. That's one of the strong benefits of the code-centric solutions - they are easier to integrate with other tools.

Table 2. Open Analytical code-centric tools

Platform	Language	License	Price	Owner	Cloud
JupyterHub	Language agnostic	Open Source	Free	NumFOCUS	Well supported
MLFlow	Java, Python, R, REST APIs	Open Source	Free (or cloud-based)	Linux Foundation	AWS, Azure, on-premise
AirFlow	Python-based Language-agnostic	Open Source	Free	Apache	All major cloud providers + other

JupyterHub - a computational environment which provides easy access to Jupyter notebooks for users. They can get the work done in their own workspaces on shared resources which can be managed efficiently by system administrators. JupyterHub runs in the cloud or on premise, and makes it possible to serve a pre-configured data science environment to any user.

MLflow is an open-source platform to manage the ML lifecycle, including experimentation, reproducibility, deployment, and a central model registry.

Apache Airflow is an open-source workflow management platform for data engineering pipelines. Airflow is written in Python, and workflows are created via Python scripts.

3 Requirements

The table below reports the functional and non-functional requirements for Policy extraction and recommendations toolkit.

Table 3. Requirements

Attribute	Description
ID	Req-01
Type	Functional
Name	Building AI pipelines
Objective	The component should provide tools for a data scientist to create AI pipelines. The data scientist should have freedom in selecting an AI algorithm and its configuration. The resulting pipeline should be easily executable through UI.
Priority	High
Attribute	Description
ID	Req-02
Type	Functional
Name	Managing AI pipelines
Objective	The component should have functionality for managing pipelines: navigating through them, executing, see the execution summary, compare results of different executions.
Priority	High
Attribute	Description
ID	Req-03
Type	Functional
Name	Managing models
Objective	The component should be able to manage trained models. It needs to track all of the artifacts and parameters that were used to train the model so the pipeline could be rerun in the future. It also should save a model so it's available for future use (inference phase, for example) and manage different versions of the same model.
Priority	High
Attribute	Description
ID	Req-04
Type	Functional
Name	Integration with other modules
Objective	This module should be integrated with VPME (UI, User management), Policy and Data management module (retrieving policies and datasets).
Priority	High
Attribute	Description

ID	Req-05
Type	Functional
Name	Code versioning
Objective	Source files that belong to an AI project should be versioned in the code repository.
Priority	High
Attribute	Description
ID	Req-06
Type	Non Functional
Name	Integration with EOSC environment
Objective	This module should be integrated with the European Open Science Cloud to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project's developments.
Priority	High
Attribute	Description
ID	Req-07
Type	Non Functional
Name	Open-Source
Objective	It's preferable that software tools we use are open-source (for security and transparency reasons)
Priority	Medium

4 Solution Design

The Policy Extraction and Recommendation module provides all necessary tools they need to build an AI pipeline and then with the resulting trained and tested AI models to design an appropriate policy by a policy maker.

There are two main goals that we had in mind while designing our solution. First goal is to analyze and select tools that would provide necessary functionality, satisfy our requirements and would integrate well with each other. Second goal is to design an UI which would glue all this functionality together and would guide a user so that at every stage of the policy extraction it's clear what is the current status and how to proceed further. When the extraction process is finished it should be easy to navigate through all existing artifacts (policies, models, pipelines).

The diagram below shows the Policy Extraction process starting from the policy and the datasets retrieved through the “Policy and Data Management” component and providing AI Models and dashboards for the Policy as an outcome for the “Policy Evaluation & Optimization” component. This process involves two actors: the Policy Maker and the AI Expert and all of the steps that need to be performed by them to achieve the goal of creating the policy’s AI models. During the process the to actors interact also with the “Policy Interpretation component” to have an interpretation of the data and the AI Models.

Figure 4. Policy extraction process

4.1 Architecture

After performing an analysis of the state of the art solutions we found none of them completely met our requirements and therefore we decided to design our system around several independent sub-components, each one implementing some specific requirements.

In the following section we will describe each sub-components and provide the details on their implementation.

4.1.1 Mapping on the Reference Architecture

Figure 5 shows the mapping of the component on the AI4PublicPolicy Reference Architecture. It interacts with Policy and Data Management component to retrieve policies and datasets, with the Policy Interpretation component to extract insights from the datasets and dashboards to interact with the AI models, the AI security component to trust data and training, the AutoML component to support public administrators in the extraction process and provides AI models and dashboards to the VPME.

Figure 5. Mapping on the reference architecture

4.1.2 Internal Architecture

The diagram below shows the internal architecture of the Policy Extraction Toolkit and how its subcomponents interact with each other:

Figure 6. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

Here is the description of the subcomponents that implement the functional requirements reported in chapter 3:

- User Interface: WEB UI that allows a data scientist and a policy maker to perform all necessary actions during the whole lifecycle of the policy.
- Code Repository: provide versioning and collaboration for AI projects and project templates;
- Open Analytical Environment: a subcomponent that provides an AI expert the environment for developing and executing AI experiments.

- Pipeline Manager: a component that is responsible for structuring AI experiments in a pipeline and tracking and comparing all the runs of the experiments with related parameters, metrics and artifacts (i.e. AI models, graphs, KPIs);
- Model Manager: a subcomponent that is responsible for managing AI models during the lifecycle of the policy extraction.

4.1.3 Components Interactions

Users start their interaction with the toolkit through Web UI. There are separate views for an AI expert and a policy maker. Using a specific view an AI expert can create an AI project by launching the open analytical environment and start developing AI experiments. The AI project includes several files, related to different stages of the experiment (data preparation, training, data visualization), which are stored in the open analytical environment and committed to the code repository when they are updated.

Pipeline manager and model manager are accessible through UI and they provide AI experts ability to manage pipelines and models. The code developed in the analytical environment is structured in a pipeline that could be managed by the pipeline manager. Models are created as a result of running pipelines and managed by the model manager for versioning and staging in different environments.

4.2 Processes

The diagrams below show the whole process of designing the policy starting from selecting a policy and creating a project by an AI expert and finishing with the policy maker approving the policy with the related model.

The first diagram shows the workflow that is performed by an AI expert. An AI expert first selects a policy to work on, selects a KPI, and creates the project, loads a dataset and starts working on the AI model development.

Figure 7. Project creation and AI model development

In the second diagram an AI expert runs several experiments by trying different parameters for the AI model and/or several different AI models. Then the model is stored together with the pipeline that applies this model to a dataset.

Figure 8. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

The diagram below shows the workflow for a policy maker. Here they can browse through available pipelines for a selected policy and KPI, run the pipeline and then select a pipeline which has the best performance. Then they approve this model as the best model for the selected policy and KPI.

Figure 9. Model/Pipeline testing & approval

On this diagram you can see the workflow that is performed by the policy maker. At this stage a policy maker selects the policy and for every available KPI for that policy he provides required input and runs the model. Then he goes to the evaluation dashboard and compares models and chooses the best one and approves it.

Figure 10: Applying model a new dataset

4.3 State of the Art Analysis

We experimented with and analyzed several solutions from both groups presented in chapter 2 and evaluated them based on the requirements that we have.

The strongest candidates that we have considered based on our requirements are KNIME, Orange, Streampipes and JupyterHub. KNIME and Orange provide a solid pipeline designer, library of AI models and an execution environment. Streampipes provides a pipeline designer and an execution environment, but its AI capabilities are weak. None of them is ideal if we take into account all our requirements.

Orange satisfies all requirements well enough except the last one: Req-06 (Integration with EOSC environment). There is no straightforward way to execute the Orange pipeline line natively in the cloud. The tool is intended to be used locally by the data scientist: pipelines can be executed locally but there is no way to deploy it and execute it in the cloud. And that is the main reason that we didn't adopt Orange as an open analytical environment for our project.

KNIME also satisfies all requirements well, it also has better integration possibilities. But there is still an issue with the Req-06 (Integration with EOSC environment). In order to execute pipelines in the cloud we need to use a commercial product KNIME Server which requires a paid license and is not

open source. For these reasons we have decided not to use this solution and started exploring code-centric solutions which may seem a bit more complex for a data scientist as they don't offer a visual pipeline designer and other convenient features. But at the same time, they provide more flexibility and freedom of integration.

Streampipes satisfies all requirements except Req-01 (Building AI pipelines) - support for this requirement is weak because although it allows building generic pipelines it doesn't have any AI-focused features. Because of that building AI pipelines would be very challenging and would require a lot of work to develop necessary plugin components for Streampipes.

Based on our analysis and requirements we narrowed our choice of the open analytical environment to JupyterHub. But we also need a tool for creating and managing pipelines.

The following table reports a summary of the SOTA comparing the features analyzed grouped by the specific requirement:

Table 4: SOTA summary

Req 01: Building AI pipelines

Features	Priority	Airflow	MLflow	Streampipes	KNIME
Visual pipeline designer	B	poor	poor	fair	good
ML specific features	B	no	good	no	good

Req 02: Managing AI pipelines

Features	Priority	Airflow	MLflow	Streampipes	KNIME
Pipeline management	B	good	poor	ok	fair
Scheduling pipelines	A	good	poor	poor	fair
Tracking experiments	C	no	good	no	fair
Visualization of metrics	A	poor	ok	poor	good

Req 03: Managing models

Features	Priority	Airflow	MLflow	Streampipes	KNIME
Models deployment	C	good	ok	ok	fair
Tracking models	A	no	good	no	fair
Tracking metadata, model parameters	B	no	good	no	fair

Req 06: Integration with EOSC environment

Features	Priority	Airflow	MLflow	Streampipes	KNIME
Jupyter notebook compatibility	A	good	good	poor	poor

Other requirements

Features	Priority	Airflow	MLflow	Streampipes	KNIME
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Community support	C	good	ok	poor	fair
Maturity	B	good	ok	poor	good
Web UI	B	ok	good	ok	good
Language-agnostic	B	good	good	poor	fair

Based on our analysis and the requirements for our platform, we decided to choose JupyterHub as Open Analytical environment and MLFlow for building, managing and executing AI pipelines.

5 Implementation

In the previous section we specified components and their functional requirements. In this section we will describe in more details how that functionality is implemented and which tools we used.

Below it is reported the list of components and the details of its implementation:

- User interface (integrated with VPME): **Vue.js** is used to build the user interface;
- Open analytical environment: **JupyterHub** which serves **Jupyter notebooks** and supports their execution;
- Code repository: **GitLab** integrated with **JupyterHub** is used;
- Pipeline manager: **MLFlow** is used for structuring, executing and tracking pipelines;
- Model management: **MLFlow** library is used to implement registering and tracking and logging functionality;

The core functionality is built around Jupyter notebooks, MLFlow and Gitlab. Gitlab provides a folder structure template which is created in the Datahub when the project is initialized. MLFlow provides features for tracking artifacts such as models, models' parameters, AI projects and pipelines. MLFlow also provides a Web UI for convenient browsing through these artifacts.

Jupyter notebooks are served by JupyterHub which provides a development and execution environment for the data scientist and allows him to create an AI experiment. Because it's a Jupyter notebook environment there is full freedom regarding the choice of the AI framework.

An AI expert works on the experiment in JupyterHub by creating several Jupyter notebooks which correspond to different stages in the AI model training process. Once the experimentation is done those notebooks could be either converted to Python or to be wrapped with Papermill so they could be executed from the command line.

5.1 User Interface

A user interface for the policy extraction component consists of two main views:

- AI Expert view
- Policy Maker view

Each of these views provides a functionality that is specific for the target role.

Figure 11. Policy extraction views

5.1.1 AI Expert view

This is a view the AI expert sees after logging into VPME. The goal of this view is to provide an interface to the AI expert which allows them to select a project, policy KPI and start working on the project. After logging into the VPME the AI expert can see the list of available projects that can be worked on.

Figure 12. AI Expert view – policies list

After selecting and opening the project a list of policy KPIs is shown. If the AI project for the selected policy KPI already exists it can be opened in JupyterHub and the work could be continued. When clicked on “View experiments” the MLFlow page will be opened with the list of experiments that have been run in the past.

If the AI project for selected policy KPI doesn’t exist yet then it could be created by clicking “Create AI project”.

Figure 13. AI Expert view – policy detail

5.1.2 Policy Maker view

This is a view the policy maker sees after logging into VPME. The goal of this view is to provide a policy maker ability to test an AI model for selected project and policy KPI. In this view the policy maker first has to choose the policy to work on.

Figure 14. Policy Maker view – policies list

Once opened the policy, the policy maker selects a KPI and can test and compare AI models using MLFlow UI (see figure 16).

Figure 15. Policy Maker view – policy detail

5.2 Code Repository

A code repository is a place which contains all source code that is needed during the process of policy extraction. All artifacts such as Jupyter notebooks, python scripts, pipelines are stored inside the AI project which follows the structure of MLFlow project.

There is a template for a new AI project which contains mostly empty files that should be updated by an AI expert during the policy model development.

This project is stored as a folder which contains all files that's needed to define and execute AI pipelines. It also includes models, project templates. Once an AI expert achieves some milestone in his work of developing the policy model, they are responsible to commit all necessary artifacts to the repository.

As a source code repository, we chose to use the GitLab. The AI expert can access the GitLab repository from the terminal window that is available inside the JupyterHub environment as shown below.

Special care is needed for managing user credentials. It's not desirable to use passwords for user authentication so we are looking at how to use tokens for that purpose.

If commit includes changes in a Jupyter notebook file (*.ipynb) then GitLab transforms the machine-readable .ipynb file into a human-readable markdown file. This greatly helps with the git diff command and keeping commits clean with clear changes.

Figure 16. Gitlab integration

5.3 Open Analytical Environment

As an analytical environment we use a JupyterHub which provides an ability to host and execute Jupyter notebooks and also provides an integrated development environment which allows an AI expert to design and execute AI experiments.

JupyterHub provides a rich set of ML (Keras, TensorFlow, PyTorch), data processing (Numpy, Pandas) and data visualization (Matplotlib) libraries. An AI expert has a full freedom to choose a set of tools based on their experience and the project at hand.

Below there is a screenshot of this environment.

Figure 17. JupyterHub interface

The main goal of the open analytical environment is to provide tools for the AI expert for creating and running AI experiments (with Jupyter notebooks), visualizing the data, trying different approaches to achieve the best performance and accuracy of the model.

After this is achieved, the next step is to make this functionality easily runnable and reusable by other users. For this purpose the notebooks should be parameterized using the Papermill library and the pipelines should be defined which allow to start execution of the AI process without any additional manual work. The next section describes pipelines and their management.

5.4 Pipeline Manager

The pipeline is a number of steps that are executed one by one. Using pipelines is a great way to chain several different stages of the AI process so that output of one stage is the input to the next one. Once all steps are finished the whole pipeline is marked as completed. Also using pipelines makes it very easy for the policy maker to run the project just by starting the pipeline and specifying its input.

With MLflow, one can build a Pipeline as a multistep workflow by making use of MLflow API for running a step and tracking within one run. This is possible because each call returns an object that holds information about the current run and can be used to store artifacts. This way, the next step that will be run will have access to whatever the previous step had produced.

MLflow Projects is an MLflow format/convention for packaging Machine Learning code in a reusable and reproducible way. In MIFlow Project there is a file MLproject file where each step is declared, its input and output.

In our implementation we used MIFlow Project format to structure the code of the Jupyter Notebooks in a reusable AI Project:

- main.py - entry point to the pipeline (could be executed both for train and test)
- download.py - script for downloading required dataset;
- process.py - data preparation and processing;
- train.py - train the model for a specific algorithm
- test.py – test the model

All the python files above contain a template code which shows what functions should be implemented so it's clear for the AI expert what is the purpose and the content of those files.

Moreover, we used MLFlow Tracking API for logging parameters, versioning models, tracking metrics, and storing artifacts (e.g. serialized model) generated during the ML Project lifecycle.

With the Tracking UI the AI Expert can see all the experiments (pipelines) and the different executions that have been run in the past, their statistics, parameters and metadata.

Figure 18. MLFlow UI

5.4.1 REST API

The Policy Extraction component provides a REST API that can be used by the VPME web application and by other AI4PublicPolicy components. Figure 2 shows a REST API definition in Swagger for the functionality related to the Pipeline manager:

Figure 19. Policy extraction component REST API (pipeline)

5.5 Model Manager

In this first version of the demonstrator the AI Models are simply managed as tagged releases of the related AI Projects in Gitlab and linked to the Policies using the Policy Management API.

In the second version we plan to use MLFlow Models and Model Registry to manage the AI models' lifecycle and the deployment in different environments.

MLflow Models is an MLflow packaging convention for models so that they can be reused later (e.g. further training). Typical usage will be model serving for batch inference with Spark or real time inference with a REST endpoint.

MLFlow Model Registry is a centralized store for managing the lifecycle of an MLflow Model (e.g., storing model, promoting model to production or archiving the model). It captures metadata about the full lifecycle to provide model lineage: which MLflow experiment produced a given model, who transitioned the model from staging to production, etc.

5.5.1 REST API

Figure 3 shows a REST API definition in Swagger for the functionality related to the model manager (will be available in the next release):

model AI Model		Find out more about our store ^
POST	<code>/model/register</code> Register model	∨
POST	<code>/model/tag</code> Tag a model	∨
GET	<code>/model/{modelId}</code> Get model by id	∨
DELETE	<code>/model/{modelId}</code> Delete model	∨
GET	<code>/model/findByStatus</code> Find models by status	∨ 🔒
GET	<code>/model/findByTags</code> Find pipelines by tags	∨ 🔒

Figure 20. Policy extraction component REST API (model)

6 Conclusions

This deliverable describes the work that was done for T5.3. The first phase was an analysis of available AI tools and fully integrated analytical environments. We analyzed fully integrated open analytical environments and also a set of independent tools which could be integrated into one solution that would satisfy our requirements. We designed workflows that would be performed by AI experts and policy makers. Then we started to map these workflows to the design and implementation of sub-components so that desired functionality is achieved.

The design for the policy extraction component presented in this deliverable fit all the requirements listed in the “Requirements” section. The following table shows how all functional requirements are satisfied.

Table 5. Functional requirements

Requirement	Sub-component	Tool
Building AI pipelines	Open analytical environment	JupyterHub
Managing AI pipelines	Pipeline manager	MLFlow
Managing models	Model manager	MLFlow
Integration with EOSC platform	-	JupyterHub, DataHub and Checkin service provided by EGI

7 Future Work

A future roadmap is to improve current features and add new features based on the feedback from the users (AI experts and policy makers) after the initial technical validation.

Some examples of the future improvements include: Integrating MLFlow Model and Model registry for model management, adding a UI designer for pipelines, improving the integration between sub-components and improving the user experience based on feedback from the pilots.

8 References

[CRISP-DM] Plotnikova V, Dumas M, Milani F. 2020. Adaptations of data mining methodologies: a systematic literature review. PeerJ Computer Science 6:e267 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.267>